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Beyond initial misanalysis: the disruptive nature of garden-path sentences processing

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the resulting representations of two types of garden-path structures in English: the main verb/reduced relative ambiguity (e.g., *The professor awarded the grant gained more attention from marine biologists*) and the transitive/intransitive ambiguity (e.g., *While the assistant shaved the actor who was overworked watched the sports news*). In contrast to previous studies, we used comprehension questions that targeted both the correct and incorrect final interpretations of the ambiguous and the disambiguating region. We successfully replicated the results of previous studies under the good-enough approach: Questions targeting the initial misanalysis yielded significantly more errors in the garden-path condition. However, we also found that this condition exhibited significantly more errors across all other comprehension questions, challenging the claim that comprehenders build a complete and faithful representation of such sentences, with the lingering of the initial misanalysis stemming from an inability to inhibit it. Our results offer robust evidence that the resulting representations of garden-path sentences are often disrupted and incomplete. We discuss these findings in relation to the good-enough approach and the self-organizing models of sentence processing, which effectively explain the co-occurrence of various representations we documented. We advocate for a broader approach in future garden-path sentence research, encouraging the inclusion of diverse sentence structures and comprehension questions that probe beyond initial misanalyses.

1. Introduction

Garden-path sentences like (1) are frequently studied in psycholinguistics due to their local syntactic ambiguity, allowing researchers to explore various aspects of sentence processing and interpretation.

(1) While Anna dressed the baby played in the crib.

The intended meaning of the sentence is that Anna dressed herself, and as she was doing so, a baby played in a crib. In this case, the verb *dressed* is used reflexively, and *the baby* is the subject of the following matrix clause. However, readers often initially interpret the first part of the sentence as if it contained a transitive verb and its direct object (*Anna dressed the baby*). This usually leads to processing difficulty when they reach the matrix verb *played*, as it cannot be incorporated in the current representation without violating grammatical rules. At this point, readers should ideally reanalyze their initial interpretation of the ambiguous region and identify the alternative, intended structure (i.e., the reflexive verb followed by the subject of the matrix clause).

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All materials and analyses (including the R script) can be found here: <https://tinyurl.com/j76ym3rw>, the preregistration can be found here: <https://tinyurl.com/ycycmea2>.

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Capturing and explaining garden-path phenomena like the one described above has become a core part of many models of sentence processing, such as the garden-path model (Frazier & Fodor, 1978; Frazier & Rayner, 1982), the constraint satisfaction based model (MacDonald et al., 1994; Trueswell et al., 1994), dependency-locality theory (Gibson, 2000), the cue-based retrieval (Van Dyke & Lewis, 2003), the good-enough approach to language comprehension (Christianson et al., 2001; Karimi & Ferreira, 2016), noisy channel processing (Levy, 2008b), or surprisal theory (Futrell et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2024; Levy, 2008a). One main point of discussion in these models is whether (and under what conditions) comprehenders create coherent and grammatically correct interpretations of such sentences after reanalysis, or whether they do something else.

For a long time, researchers assumed that the interpretation of such sentences was an all-or-nothing phenomenon (Fodor & Inoue, 1998; Frazier & Rayner, 1982; Inoue & Fodor, 1995). Comprehenders were thought to either fully and correctly analyze garden-path sentences or fail entirely. However, in the last 20 years, multiple studies (especially within the good-enough approach) have shown that this is not always the case (e.g., Christianson et al., 2001, 2006; Huang & Ferreira, 2021; Malyutina & den Ouden, 2016; Patson et al., 2009; Qian et al., 2018; Slattery et al., 2013; Sturt, 2007). According to current data, comprehenders often reanalyze the sentence only partially. While much of the input is interpreted correctly, the initial analysis (e.g., *Anna dressed the baby*) often lingers even after the entire sentence has been read. For the sake of brevity, we follow the terminology of the previous studies and use the term “misanalysis” to refer to this initially created analysis in the rest of the article. With that said, it is important to point out that the usage of this term might be misleading as it implies that this analysis is, in some way, a mistake (and is recognized as such). This implication is problematic when we consider the fact that the misanalysis in question can also be created and maintained as a result of a good-enough processing strategy or as a way to salvage a parsing failure, in which case it might be (a) the only analysis of the sentence that was created by a comprehender and (b) a result of a common parsing strategy.

Evidence for lingering misanalysis has been acquired through various methods. Christianson et al. (2001) used comprehension questions to probe the final interpretation of sentences like (1) and found that the question targeting the initial misanalysis (e.g., *Did Anna dress the baby?*) was answered correctly only 40% of the time. In other words, most participants maintained the initial misanalysis even after reanalysis. At the same time, the question asking about the correct interpretation of the disambiguating region (e.g., *Did the baby play in the crib?*) produced nearly no errors, with a response accuracy of around 90%, suggesting that this region was interpreted correctly. Similar results supporting the presence of lingering misanalysis were obtained through a paraphrasing task (Patson et al., 2009) and a picture selection task (Malyutina & den Ouden, 2016).

Since the above-mentioned studies mostly rely on offline measurements, it is possible that the documented interpretations do not arise directly during parsing but only as a result of reading the comprehension questions or viewing the pictures, both of which might (re)activate the related interpretation in people’s minds. However, these phenomena have also been documented using online paradigms. Probably the most famous example is an eye-tracking study conducted by Slattery et al. (2013), where the authors observed the presence of a gender mismatch effect on the reflexive pronoun in sentences like (2). For the gender mismatch effect to occur here, *David’s mother* must be interpreted as the subject of the matrix clause (*grew worried*) and, by extension, also of *gave himself*. The authors interpret this as evidence of successful reanalysis.

- (2) After the bank manager telephoned David’s mother grew worried and gave himself approximately 5 days to reply.

In a separate experiment, they also documented the presence of lingering misanalysis in sentences like (3), where readers slowed down in the *himself off* region due to interference between the intended analysis and the initial misanalysis (*Frank dried off the truck*).

- (3) While Frank dried off the truck that was dark green was peed on by a stray dog, Frank quickly finished drying himself off then yelled out the window at the dog.

Based on these results, the authors claim that people most likely create a globally coherent, grammatical, and correct syntactic representation of garden-path sentences during reanalysis but fail to inhibit the initial misinterpretation. This initial interpretation lingers in their memory and interferes with the newly created intended interpretation of the sentence. This explanation is also favored by Huang and Ferreira (2021), who successfully replicated Slattery et al.'s (2013) experiment with improved stimuli. However, Huang and Ferreira (2021) also propose an alternative explanation: Comprehenders may not build a coherent, global representation of the sentence. Instead, they might create multiple local representations that cannot be combined into a grammatical whole (e.g., *the bank manager telephoned David's mother* and *David's mother grew worried*).

Although current data are consistent with both explanations, the latter option – that coherent representations of garden-path sentences might often not be created at all – has received relatively little attention. This may be because most studies probing the interpretations of garden-path sentences tend to focus on the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region (further referred to as AMBMIS) and the correct interpretation of the disambiguating region (further referred to as DISCOR). The results obtained this way almost always support the former explanation. Specifically, what we typically find in the literature is the following combination of sentence structures and comprehension questions:

- (4) While Anna dressed the baby played in the crib.
 a. Did Anna dress the baby? AMBMIS
 b. Did the baby play in the crib? DISCOR

The well-documented low response accuracy to AMBMIS and high response accuracy to DISCOR align with the suggestion that, aside from the lingering misanalysis, the representations readers build during reanalysis are globally coherent and faithful to the input, leaving little reason to assume otherwise. However, when studies focus on other regions of these sentences, the situation becomes more complex.

For example, in one of their experiments, Christianson et al. (2006) worked with sentences similar to (4) but asked participants a different question: *Did Anna dress herself?* This question specifically tests whether readers managed to identify and maintain the intended analysis of the ambiguous region after reanalyzing the sentence, which should occur if they had created a correct, globally coherent parse. If participants succeeded, the response accuracy to this question should be similar for both garden-path sentences and their non-ambiguous counterparts.

However, the results showed that not only did the accuracy drop in the garden-path condition, but the decrease was quite substantial, especially for the older group of participants, whose accuracy in the garden-path condition was only 50% (compared to 80% in the non-garden-path condition). This pattern of results might still be consistent with the idea of a global parse if we assume that the low response accuracy is due to interference between the intended interpretation of the ambiguous region and the initial misanalysis (*Anna dressed the baby* vs. *Anna dressed herself*). However, it raises the question of why readers favor the initial misinterpretation over the intended one, even though the latter should have more support due to factors like the recency effect, acquiescence bias, or structural similarities to the comprehension question. A more likely explanation is that people simply do not always successfully reinterpret the ambiguous region.

Further evidence comes from recent studies on Czech. Chromý (2022) showed that comprehenders tend to misinterpret not only the ambiguous region of garden-path sentences but also other parts of the sentence. In sentences like (5), response accuracy in the garden-path condition was lower for all four questions listed below.

- (5) Kluc-i honi-li ps-a a kočk-u v
 Boy-NOM.M.PL CHASE-3PL.M.PST dog-ACC.M.SG and cat-ACC.F.SG in
 podkrov-í znepokojova-li šediv-í hlodavc-i.
 attic-LOC.N.SG worry-3PL.M.PST gray-NOM.M.PL rodents-NOM.M.PL
 ‘The boys chased a dog and the gray rodents in the attic worried a cat.’

- a. Did the boys chase the cat?
- b. Did the rodents worry the cat?
- c. Did the boys chase the dog?
- d. Did the rodents worry the dog?

In this structure, the region *psa a kočku* (*a dog and a cat*) is initially interpreted as a coordination of noun phrases, with *a cat* as the object of the first verb, *chased* (*the boys chased a dog and a cat*). However, the conjunction *and* actually connects two separate clauses, with the second one having an object-verb-subject (OVS) word order. Therefore, *a cat* should be interpreted as the object of the second verb, *worried* (*the rodents worried a cat*). The intended meaning of the sentence is that the boys chased the dog, and, as they were doing so, the rodents worried the cat.

Since the question *Did the boys chase the cat?* targets the initial misanalysis, lower response accuracy is expected. However, the response accuracy was also similarly low for the question *Did the rodents worry the cat?*, which targets the correct analysis of the disambiguating region (only 58% compared to 92% in the non-garden-path condition). This suggests that in many cases neither the ambiguous region nor the disambiguating region was interpreted correctly. Moreover, response accuracy in the garden-path condition was also lower for the other two questions, even though these should have been relatively easy to answer and unaffected by the ambiguity.

The author explains this finding as a result of cognitive overload and confusion, which prevent comprehenders from creating a coherent parse of the sentence. Instead, readers rely on inferences and their memory of the lexical content of the sentences to compensate for the absence of a coherent representation. Similar results might also occur if comprehenders create multiple local parses (e.g., *the boys chased the cat and the dog; the rodents worried the cat and the dog*), which then interfere with each other. Either way, if people constructed a grammatical global parse of these sentences and the only issue was the initial misanalysis, we would not expect to see such a pattern of results. For instance, *the dog* should remain attached to *chased* at all times because the verb is transitive and requires an object.

Another recent study on Czech further demonstrates that readers do not always create globally coherent and correct representations of garden-path sentences. Ceháková and Chromý (2023) used a different type of structure to show that the final interpretations of such sentences can vary considerably, ranging from globally coherent and grammatical to completely incoherent. Participants read sentences like (6) and responded to questions targeting the interpretations of both the ambiguous region and the disambiguating region.

- (6) Ostražit-ý policist-a prohledal obchodnic-i
 alert-NOM.M.SG policeman-NOM.M.SG search-3SG.M.PST shopkeeper-DAT.F.SG
 před prodejn-ou dodávk-u a odje-l na
 in front of shop-INST.F.SG van-ACC.F.SG and leave-3SG.M.PST for
 služebn-u.
 station-ACC.F.SG
 ‘An alert policeman searched a shopkeeper’s van in front of her shop and left for the station.’

In this sentence, the noun *obchodníci* (*the shopkeeper*) is initially interpreted as the direct object but later needs to be reanalyzed as an adjunct (specifically, an external possessor) because the object position must be occupied by another noun, *dodávku* (*the van*). Thus, comprehenders might misanalyze the beginning of the sentence as *the policeman searched the shopkeeper*, while the intended meaning is *the policeman searched the shopkeeper’s van*.

In addition to documenting the lingering misanalysis in this type of structure, the authors also presented another finding: comprehenders did not always successfully incorporate the disambiguating region into their final representations. The response accuracy to the question targeting the interpretation of this region (*Did the policeman search the van?*) was significantly lower in the garden-path condition, although the effect size was small.

The authors also used open-ended questions, such as *What did the policeman do?* The responses further supported the possibility that coherent global structures are sometimes not created at all. Most participants provided responses that corresponded to the intended meaning of the sentence (*the policeman searched the van/the shopkeeper's van*) or to the initial misanalysis (*the policeman searched the shopkeeper*). However, in other cases, they explicitly stated their confusion or uncertainty about the meaning of the sentence (e.g., *I don't know, the sentence doesn't make sense*), created interpretations that were not licensed by the input (*the policeman searched the shopkeeper and the van*), or developed multiple local interpretations that they pitted against each other (*the policeman searched the shopkeeper or the van*).

To summarize, multiple studies documented that the disambiguating region of garden-path sentences is often interpreted correctly but the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region lingers simultaneously. These findings were obtained mainly through methodologies that targeted only the two regions in question – the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region and the correct analysis of the disambiguating region. Such findings can be explained in two main ways: either that readers manage to build the intended globally coherent representation during reanalysis but fail to inhibit the initial misanalysis in their memory, or that they build multiple locally coherent representations instead of a global one. While the first option is often favored in literature, most results of the current experiments are consistent with both explanations. However, studies that do not limit comprehension probes to the two regions mentioned above and explore how other parts of garden-path sentences are interpreted suggest that comprehenders might settle on multiple locally coherent interpretations or generally disrupted interpretations more often than is usually assumed. These studies consistently show that the ambiguous region is often not interpreted correctly at all and that other parts of the sentence might also be misinterpreted.

These findings might be of interest to multiple theories of sentence processing. First, knowing that people often form disrupted, locally coherent representations would provide important insights into the debate about self-consistency (e.g., Paape et al., 2023; Tabor et al., 2004) and support models that already assume such representations can arise for various reasons (e.g., self-organized sentence processing [Smith et al., 2021; Tabor et al., 2004] or the good-enough approach). Understanding that readers do not successfully reanalyze garden-path sentences would shed new light on the debate within the good-enough approach, particularly regarding the question of what exactly is incomplete about the reanalysis, whether it is the inhibition of the initial interpretation or the final representation itself, with evidence supporting the latter. Finally, it would further emphasize the diversity in sentence processing, showing that final representations of sentences are not limited to extreme cases of complete success or complete failure but are, in fact, quite varied.

2. Current study

In the current study, we aim to follow up on the experiments performed by Christianson et al. (2006), Chromý (2022), and Ceháková and Chromý (2023) to explore the interpretations of garden-path sentences in more detail. Our goal is to test whether the ambiguous and disambiguating regions of these sentences are interpreted correctly, as is often assumed, or whether the final interpretations are more disrupted. We are using comprehension probes that focus on both the correct analysis and potential misanalysis of each of these regions. Our reasoning is that the two comprehension questions typically found in the literature on garden-path sentences provide only a limited view of what the final representations look like.

Imagine that we explore the interpretation of the sentence *While Anna dressed the baby played in the crib* using the two questions presented in (7):

- (7) a. Did Anna dress the baby?
b. Did the baby play in the crib?

Question (7a) targets the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region. Participants often give a positive response to this question even though the correct interpretation of the sentence should warrant a negative one. The high amount of positive responses documented in the literature suggests that the initial misanalysis lingers. The question is why. It could be that people interpreted the ambiguous region correctly, but the interference from the initial misanalysis still active in their memory is too strong. Alternatively, people may not have analyzed this region correctly in the first place, meaning the initial misanalysis is, in fact, the only analysis they created. We cannot determine which option we are dealing with without asking participants about the correct analysis: *Did Anna dress herself?*

Many studies also assume that the ambiguous region was successfully reinterpreted because question (7b) is often answered correctly (or because the gender mismatch effect is documented on a pronoun related to the ambiguous region, as mentioned above). However, both the gender mismatch effect and the correct response to this question only show that people successfully attached the disambiguating verb to the preceding noun. They do not demonstrate that the noun was detached from its original position or that the first verb was reinterpreted. This conclusion is logical if we assume that the readers aim to build a globally coherent, grammatical structure. In this case, it would be impossible for *the baby* to occupy two syntactic positions simultaneously or for a transitive verb to lack an object. Nevertheless, this conclusion is not directly warranted by the data and should not be made automatically, especially since studies suggest that locally coherent structures inconsistent with the global, grammatical representation of the input might actually arise during processing (Christianson et al., 2017; Paape & Vasishth, 2016; Tabor et al., 2004).

Considering the possibility that comprehenders create multiple locally coherent representations, we should ensure that the correct interpretation of the disambiguating region is the only interpretation created. Knowing that participants successfully attached the disambiguating region to one noun does not necessarily mean they did not attempt to attach it to other nouns in the sentence as well (e.g., *Anna played in the crib*). Once again, this should not be possible if we assume that processing strictly follows the rules of grammar, but we should not make this assumption until we actually test that option.

In the current study, we explore the final interpretations of two well-known types of English garden-path sentences in two experiments, conducted in a single experimental session with the same participant sample. Experiment 1 examined main verb/reduced relative (MV/RR) ambiguity, as in the sentence (8).

- (8) The professor awarded the grant gained more attention from marine biologists.

The garden-path effect in MV/RR sentences like (8) stems from the ambiguity of the verb form *awarded*, which is initially interpreted as an active past participle and thus a matrix clause verb (*the professor awarded the grant [to someone] . . .*). However, it is actually used as a passive participle in a reduced relative clause (*the professor [who was] awarded the grant [by someone] . . .*).

Ideally, comprehenders should realize that their initial interpretation was incorrect once they reach the disambiguating verb *gained* that would lack a subject if the current analysis is maintained. The only grammatically correct solution is to attach the verb to the noun *professor*. However, it is also possible to create a locally licit string by attaching it to the noun *grant*, which might further complicate the reanalysis.

Experiment 2 targeted the transitive/intransitive (NP/Z) ambiguity, as in (9).

- (9) While the assistant shaved the actor who was overworked watched the sports news.

Here, the verb *shaved* is initially interpreted as transitive, followed by the direct object *the actor* (meaning that *the assistant shaved the actor*). However, it is actually reflexive (*the assistant shaved himself*), with *the actor* serving as the subject of the following matrix clause (*the actor watched the sports news*). Similar to the MV/RR sentences, the reanalysis should be triggered when comprehenders reach the matrix clause verb (*watched*), as otherwise it would lack a subject. Unlike with the MV/RR sentences, though, the main verb should be attached to the closest possible noun (*the actor*), not to the first noun in the sentence (*the assistant*). Thus, in this case, the locally licit string is also globally licit and consistent with the intended grammatical representation. Nevertheless, people might still attempt to attach the verb to the first noun in the sentence.

In both experiments, we examined the effects of ambiguity on comprehension accuracy using four different types of questions specifically targeting: the correct analysis of the ambiguous region (AMBCOR), a potential misanalysis of the ambiguous region (AMB MIS), the correct analysis of the disambiguating region (DISCOR), and a potential misanalysis of the disambiguating region (DIS MIS). This allowed us to gain a deeper understanding of the resulting representations that comprehenders built, providing insights that surpass those achieved in previous studies on such structures in English.

2.1. Hypotheses

Based on the results of previous studies examining the processing of MV/RR and NP/Z structures, as well as studies on Czech garden-path sentences, we propose four hypotheses, three targeting response accuracy and one targeting reaction times during reading:

- (1) While reading, participants will experience garden-path effects in both sentence types. Reaction times will be higher in the disambiguating and spillover regions of the MV/RR and NP/Z sentences in the garden-path condition.
- (2) Consistent with previous studies, we expect the ambiguous region of the garden-path sentences to be misanalyzed in both sentence types, with this misanalysis lingering over time. Consequently, response accuracy to AMB MIS, the question targeting the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region, will be lower in the garden-path condition.
- (3) If comprehenders successfully reanalyze the sentence while inhibiting the initial misanalysis, as proposed by Slattery et al. (2013), response accuracy for the remaining comprehension questions (AMBCOR, DISCOR, DIS MIS) should be similar across conditions. More specifically, comprehenders should successfully attach the disambiguating region to the existing structure, leading to accurate responses both to the DISCOR question, which tests whether they created the correct attachment, and to the DIS MIS question, which tests whether they attempted to attach this region elsewhere. Additionally, successful reanalysis of the ambiguous region should result in correct responses to the AMBCOR question.

In contrast, if comprehenders fail to build a coherent representation of the sentence, as suggested by Christianson et al. (2006), Chromý (2022), and Ceháková and Chromý (2023), response accuracy should be lower across all comprehension questions in the garden-path condition. Comprehenders may fail to attach the disambiguating verb to its intended position, leading to lower response accuracy to DISCOR. They might also consider other attachment options, leading to lower response accuracy to DIS MIS. Finally, they might also fail to reanalyze the ambiguous region, leading to lower response accuracy to AMBCOR.

- (4) Finally, if comprehenders create multiple locally licit strings (treelets), as proposed by Huang and Ferreira (2021), response accuracy patterns may differ between MV/RR and NP/Z sentences. In both sentence types, the ambiguous region may initially be misinterpreted, resulting in a locally well-formed but globally incorrect parse (e.g., *The professor awarded the grant* in MV/RR sentences and *While the assistant shaved the actor* in NP/Z sentences). However, the interpretation of the disambiguating region should differ. If comprehenders indeed rely on creating multiple locally licit strings, this region will be misanalyzed more often in MV/RR

sentences. If comprehenders attempt to solve the disambiguation by attaching the currently subject-less verb to the closest possible noun in the MV/RR ambiguity, it will lead to the creation of a locally plausible but globally incorrect string, such as *the grant gained more attention*. The correct analysis of this region may not even be created because the verb already found an attachment site (i.e., *the professor gained more attention*) or it might deal with interference from the misanalysis. This will result in lower response accuracy to the DISMIS (i.e., *Did the grant gain more attention?*) and DISCOR (i.e., *Did the professor gain more attention?*) questions in both the garden-path and non-garden-path condition. The opposite effect is expected for NP/Z sentences, where the locally plausible analysis of the disambiguating region (*the actor who was overworked watched the sports news*) is also globally correct, making successful interpretation of the disambiguating region easier.

3. Methods

3.1. Data availability

All materials and analyses (including the R script) can be found at the following link: <https://tinyurl.com/j76ym3rw>, and the preregistration can be found at the following link: <https://tinyurl.com/jycyme2>.

3.2. Ethics approval

Research ethics board approval for this study was acquired from the Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Arts, Charles University (reference no. UKFF/624176/2023). Participation in the experiments was voluntary, and all participants provided written informed consent. All data used in the current analyses were fully anonymized.

3.3. Participants

We recruited 178 participants with American English as their first language via Prolific, applying several key filtering criteria for inclusion in the experiment. Participants were required to be between 19 and 26 years old, have an active student status, report no literacy difficulties, and have been raised speaking only English. These criteria ensured comparability with previous studies, which primarily tested undergraduate students, and helped minimize potential confounding factors, such as language interference or general reading difficulties.

Two participants were excluded due to low response accuracy (with a cutoff set at 75% correct answers). These participants were replaced through Prolific. Additionally, one participant was excluded because of a technical issues with data saving and another due to an age report that exceeded our restriction (88 years). The resulting sample used for analysis consisted of 176 participants (115 women, 53 men, 8 nonbinary), with a mean age of 21.85 years ($SD = 1.99$ years). The average response accuracy for filler items was 95.33% ($SD = 4.1$).

3.4. Procedure

The experiment was conducted online using the PC Ixbox Farm platform (Zehr & Schwarz, 2018). Before the experimental trials, participants completed a brief demographic questionnaire, providing their age, gender, first language, and whether they experience any reading difficulties in their life (such as dyslexia).

After completing the questionnaire, participants were given three practice items to familiarize themselves with the procedure. The experiment used a moving-window, self-paced reading task where participants saw a series of underscores representing a sentence. Pressing a button revealed the first

word, and with each subsequent press, the current word disappeared and the next word appeared. Once the participants finished reading the sentence, they pressed the button again to proceed to a yes or no comprehension question about the sentence content. Half of the questions had “yes” as the correct answer and half had “no.” In total, participants read 118 sentences, comprising 70 filler items and 24 experimental sentences from each of the two parallel experiments (see below).

The items were randomized for each participant, with experimental sentences never appearing consecutively. Additionally, a Latin square design was used to counterbalance conditions for each participant. Each participant encountered 12 sentences with MV/RR ambiguity and 12 sentences with NP/Z ambiguity (and 12 unambiguous counterparts of each type). Since four types of comprehension questions were used, each participant was presented with three examples from each condition.

3.5. Materials

We used two types of garden-path sentences, 24 NP/Z sentences and 24 MV/RR sentences. Participants saw all the sentences of each type in one of eight conditions. For both types, we manipulated two variables – ambiguity (ambiguous, unambiguous) and question type (ambcor, ambmis, discor, dismis). Participants thus saw three NP/Z and three MV/RR sentences from each condition, following a 2×4 within-subject factorial design.

The MV/RR sentences were taken directly from the materials used by Huang et al. (2024), with new comprehension questions created specifically for our experiment. The unambiguous condition was generated by using the nonreduced version of the relative clause (e.g., *the professor who was awarded the grant* instead of *the professor awarded the grant*). An item example is presented in Table 1.

The NP/Z sentences were selected from the materials used by Huang and Ferreira (2021). We chose 24 sentences featuring verbs that describe reflexive or reciprocal activities (e.g., *to dress, to hug*). The original sentences were similar to those used by Slattery et al. (2013), as shown in example (2). We shortened the stimuli to better match the length of the MV/RR sentences, omitting the final clause of each sentence (e.g., *... and gave himself approximately 5 days to reply*), as it was not relevant to our experiment. We also made minor adjustments for consistency (e.g., using the same relative pronoun in all stimuli) and corrected some typographical errors. The unambiguous sentences were created by adding a comma after the ambiguous verb (e.g., *While the assistant shaved, the actor . . .*). An example item is presented in Table 2.

Overall, participants were presented with 48 experimental sentences and 72 grammatical filler sentences in random order (120 sentences in total). Each sentence was followed by a comprehension question targeting one of the regions of interest. The number of correct yes and no responses was balanced throughout the experiment.

Table 1. Item example from Experiment 1: MV/RR ambiguity

Ambiguity	Sentence	QuesType	Question	Correct
Yes	The professor awarded the grant gained more attention from marine biologists.	ambcor	Did someone award the grant to the professor?	Yes
		ambmis	Did the professor award the grant?	No
		discor	Did the professor gain more attention?	Yes
		dismis	Did the grant gain more attention?	No
No	The professor who was awarded the grant gained more attention from marine biologists.	ambcor	Did someone award the grant to the professor?	Yes
		ambmis	Did the professor award the grant?	No
		discor	Did the professor gain more attention?	Yes
		dismis	Did the grant gain more attention?	No

Table 2. Item example from Experiment 2: NP/Z ambiguity

Ambiguity	Sentence	QuesType	Question	Correct
Yes	While the assistant shaved the actor who was overworked watched the sports news.	ambcor	Did the assistant shave himself?	Yes
		ambmis	Did the assistant shave the actor?	No
		discor	Did the actor watch the sports news?	Yes
		dismis	Did the assistant watch the sports news?	No
No	While the assistant shaved, the actor who was overworked watched the sports news.	ambcor	Did the assistant shave himself?	Yes
		ambmis	Did the assistant shave the actor?	No
		discor	Did the actor watch the sports news?	Yes
		dismis	Did the assistant watch the sports news?	No

3.6. Data analysis

We used the `lme4` package (Bates et al., 2014) in the R programming language (version 4.3.2) for statistical analysis. For the analysis of reaction times, we used a linear mixed-effects regression, while we used a generalized linear mixed-effects regression to analyze response accuracy.

All models included participant and item as random effects, and random slopes were determined based on the principles outlined by Bates et al. (2015). The analysis of reaction times was conducted using two separate models for the two types of ambiguities. Both models included only the main effect of ambiguity, which was sum contrast coded (with garden-path sentences coded as 0.5 and controls as -0.5). The analysis of response accuracy was performed in one comprehensive model that incorporated the presence of ambiguity (using the same coding as above) and the type of garden-path structure (sum contrast coded with MV/RR as 0.5 and NP/Z as -0.5) in interaction. This interaction was further nested under the main effect of question type (treatment coded with the ambiguity misanalysis question as the reference value).

The data were trimmed according to the rules set in the preregistration. First, clearly outlying reaction times (above 10,000 ms) were excluded. Second, reaction times below 100 ms (indicative of accidental button presses) were also excluded. Third, reaction times were log-transformed, and the higher cutoff point was set as the mean log-transformed reaction time plus 2.5 standard deviations of the mean, which was 1,092.12 ms (or 6.99 log(ms)). This trimming procedure resulted in 2.41% reaction times being excluded.

4. Results

4.1. Reaction times

Reaction times for the disambiguating regions and two spillover regions in both experiments are shown in Figure 1

4.1.1. MV/RR ambiguity

The linear mixed-effects models yielded significant effects of the presence of ambiguity for all three analyzed regions: disambiguating region ($\beta = 0.032$, $SE = 0.011$, $t = 2.971$, $p = .007$), disambiguating region + 1 ($\beta = 0.112$, $SE = 0.014$, $t = 8.053$, $p < .001$), and disambiguating region + 2 ($\beta = 0.09$, $SE = 0.013$, $t = 6.992$, $p < .001$).

Figure 1. Log-transformed reaction times for the two ambiguity types contrasting results for garden-path and control sentences.

4.1.2. NP/Z ambiguity

As in the case of MV/RR ambiguity, the model showed significant effects of ambiguity in all three regions: disambiguating region ($\beta = 0.031$, $SE = 0.009$, $t = 3.369$, $p = .003$), disambiguating region + 1 ($\beta = 0.057$, $SE = 0.009$, $t = 6.537$, $p < .001$), and disambiguating region + 2 ($\beta = 0.037$, $SE = 0.012$, $t = 3.159$, $p = .003$).

4.2. Response accuracy

The response accuracy for both experiments is shown in Figure 2. The logit mixed-effects model contained ambiguity presence as a random slope for items and an interaction between ambiguity presence and type of garden-path structure for participants. The model yielded the following results:

- (1) The initial misanalysis question (AMBMIS) yielded lower response accuracy than the question targeting correct interpretation of the ambiguity (AMBCOR): $\beta = 0.445$, $SE = 0.074$, $z = 6.014$, $p < .001$, the question targeting the correct interpretation of the disambiguating word (DISCOR): $\beta = 3.619$, $SE = 0.18$, $z = 20.126$, $p < .001$, and the question targeting the misanalysis of the disambiguating word (DISMIS): $\beta = 0.4$, $SE = 0.078$, $z = 5.107$, $p < .001$.

Figure 2. Response accuracy for the two ambiguity types contrasting results for garden-path and control sentences.

- (2) For the DISMIS question type, there was a significant effect of garden-path type ($\beta = -2.531$, $SE = 0.237$, $z = -10.695$, $p < .001$).
- (3) The presence of ambiguity led to lower response accuracy for all four question types: AMBMIS ($\beta = -1.67$, $SE = 0.134$, $z = -12.427$, $p < .001$), AMBCOR ($\beta = -1.247$, $SE = 0.136$, $z = -9.177$, $p < .001$), DISCOR ($\beta = -2.325$, $SE = 0.359$, $z = -6.515$, $p < .001$), and DISMIS ($\beta = -0.777$, $SE = 0.145$, $z = -5.365$, $p < .001$).
- (4) There was a significant effect of the interaction between the garden-path type and presence of ambiguity for the DISCOR question type ($\beta = -1.881$, $SE = 0.705$, $z = -2.667$, $p = .008$).

5. Discussion

Our study focused on probing the final interpretations of two well-known types of English garden-path sentences: NP/Z and MV/RR ambiguities. While previous research has primarily concentrated on the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region and the correct interpretation of the disambiguating region, our experiment went further by also including questions targeting the correct analysis of the ambiguous region and the potential misanalysis of the disambiguating region. In other words, we sought to determine whether garden-path sentences are truly interpreted faithfully to the input, as is often assumed.

In our study, we used MV/RR sentences like (10) and NP/Z sentences like (11).

(10) The professor awarded the grant gained more attention from marine biologists.

(11) While the assistant shaved the actor who was overworked watched the sports news.

The sentences were accompanied by four comprehension questions targeting both the ambiguous and disambiguating region to assess whether these regions were interpreted correctly. If the final interpretations were faithful to the input and globally coherent (aside from the lingering misanalysis), as suggested by Slattery et al. (2013), we would expect participants to struggle primarily with the question focused on the misanalysis of the ambiguous region while performing relatively well on the other three questions. However, if the final representations were more disrupted, the garden-path condition would result in lower response accuracy across all questions. We observed a clear garden-path effect in both sentence types, indicated by elevated reaction times at the disambiguating regions (*gained*, *watched*) and the two spillover regions.

Response accuracy in the unambiguous condition was generally high across all four questions for both sentence types, with one exception: the question targeting a potential misanalysis of the disambiguating region in the MV/RR sentences. Here, response accuracy was rather low, which we discuss in more detail later.

In the ambiguous condition, several important findings emerged. We replicated the lingering misanalysis effect found in previous studies but also found robust evidence suggesting that the ambiguous region is often not analyzed correctly and that the disambiguating region gets misanalyzed as well, especially in the MV/RR sentences.

Similarly to previous studies, response accuracy to the question targeting the initial misanalysis was well below 50% for both the MV/RR and NP/Z sentences. In most cases, participants indicated that *the professor awarded the grant to someone* or that *the assistant shaved the actor*, even though such interpretations were not licensed by the global syntactic structure and should have been inhibited if readers had analyzed the sentences fully and correctly. We also observed very high response accuracy for the question targeting the correct interpretation of the disambiguating region in both sentence types (once again consistent with previous studies). This question tested whether comprehenders attached the disambiguating verb to the correct noun in the sentence (i.e., *the professor* in the MV/RR sentences and *the actor* in the NP/Z sentences). As mentioned earlier, comprehenders were quite successful in answering this question, with

approximately 90% responding that *the professor gained more attention* and that *the actor watched the sports news*. However, the ambiguous condition still produced more incorrect responses than the unambiguous condition, indicating that participants did not always succeed in this step.

When we asked about the correct analysis of the ambiguous region (e.g., *Did someone award the grant to the professor?* for the MV/RR sentences and *Did the assistant shave himself?* for the NP/Z sentences), participants provided only around 50% correct responses for both sentence types, closely aligning with the findings of Christianson et al. (2006). Given that our experiments offered just two response options – yes and no – this accuracy rate is effectively at the level of chance. This suggests that when faced with these comprehension questions, participants were often guessing the correct answer. Another option is that half of the participants was successful in reanalyzing the sentence while the other half failed. Since our data for this question are distributed rather normally than bimodally, it does not seem to be the case (and even such results would still mean that a large number of participants failed to reanalyze the ambiguous region).

There are two main explanations for this pattern. First, participants may not have discovered the correct interpretation of the ambiguous region at all, leaving them with no relevant information to answer the comprehension question, which led them to guess. Second, participants may have identified the intended interpretation, but interference from their initial misanalysis was too strong, preventing them from either confidently settling on the correct interpretation during processing or successfully recalling it when answering the question.

The issue with the second explanation is that, as we mentioned earlier, if comprehenders did successfully reanalyze the ambiguous region, it is unclear why this correct analysis would be overpowered by the initial misanalysis. The correct interpretation should have an advantage: It is more recent, grammatically licit, and reactivated by the comprehension question. Additionally, acquiescence bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003) should also favor the correct response here. Given this, it seems more plausible that the ambiguous region was not successfully reanalyzed and that the initial misanalysis was, in fact, the only interpretation the participants formed.

We thank an anonymous reviewer for pointing out that the low response accuracy to this question in MV/RR sentences might also stem from the fact that it does not target events that were explicitly described in the sentence. Participants might legitimately answer “no” to *Did someone award the grant to the professor?* because they interpreted the question more literally and the event of someone being awarded a grant was not the direct topic of the sentence (it did not actively happen in the scenario). In this case, answering “no” would not be caused by the lack of reanalysis but by the way the question was interpreted. Nevertheless, we also observe a similar effect in NP/Z sentences, where the event described in the question (*Did the assistant shave himself?*) does actively happen in the scenario described by the sentence. The lower response accuracy might be caused by other factors unrelated to the syntactic structure, however (e.g., the participants interpreting the assistant as feminine). These effects can explain the generally lower response accuracy to this question but cannot, however, explain the difference between the ambiguous and unambiguous condition we documented. The interaction with ambiguity suggests that something else is going on. Nevertheless, we should bear in mind that we cannot really be sure how participants interpreted the questions and how this interpretation influenced their representation of the previously read sentence and that our results might be influenced by task-related effects. We discuss this option in more detail later.

Regarding the disambiguating region, as noted earlier, participants were highly successful in attaching the disambiguating verb to the correct noun in both sentence types. However, our findings indicate that this was not the only interpretation participants created. They also showed a tendency to attach the disambiguating verb to the other noun in the sentence (e.g., *the grant gained more attention*, *the assistant watched the sports news*), even though such interpretations were grammatically incorrect.

This tendency was even more pronounced in the MV/RR sentences, where the string *the grant gained more attention* was both locally coherent and plausible (with the noun *grant* appearing directly

next to the verb). In both the ambiguous and unambiguous conditions, response accuracy was low, although the effect was stronger in the ambiguous condition.

This aligns with the local coherence effects described by Tabor et al. (2004) that the parser may entertain locally coherent analyses even if they are not globally grammatical, either due to the self-organizing nature of processing or uncertainty about prior input. These local coherence effects may also explain the differences in effect sizes on the disambiguating region. Participants took longer to process this region in the MV/RR sentences because they were considering both the locally plausible and the intended analysis. In contrast, reaction times were faster and response accuracy was much higher in the NP/Z condition, where the disambiguating verb and the “incorrect” noun were separated by multiple words, including the “correct” noun. Nonetheless, the disambiguating region exhibited a tendency to be misanalyzed in both sentence types.

Similarly to other studies (e.g., Huang et al., 2024), we observed considerable between-item variability in response accuracy for all questions except *discor* in MV/RR sentences and for the *ambcor* and *ambimis* questions in the NP/Z sentences. A plot showing response accuracy for each condition across individual items can be found in [Appendix A](#). This item-wise variability should ideally be studied further since it may offer deeper insights into the mechanisms and factors influencing sentence processing.

Although the items share a similar syntactic structure, they differ semantically and pragmatically. Previous studies have shown that plausibility can influence the success of inhibiting the initial misanalysis (Christianson et al., 2001; Garnsey et al., 1997; Maljutina & den Ouden, 2016; Nakamura & Arai, 2016), although some studies have reported conflicting findings (Jacob & Felser, 2016; Qian et al., 2018). Differences between items may also be explained by noisy-channel processing, which is discussed later in the article. Specifically, aside from plausibility differences, some items may be more susceptible to word addition or deletion, potentially influencing the final representations comprehenders construct. However, identifying the specific factors at play would require a more detailed analysis beyond the scope of the present study.

To summarize, the garden-path (ambiguous) condition led to lower response accuracy across all four question types. This result mirrors the findings of Chromý (2022) and Ceháková and Chromý (2023), who documented a similar effect with two types of Czech garden-path sentences. The final interpretation of garden-path sentences in our experiment appeared more disrupted than that of their unambiguous counterparts, regardless of which region was examined. Our results also suggest that people misanalyze the ambiguous region of garden-path sentences and fail to reanalyze it successfully. Furthermore, on reaching the disambiguating region, participants attempted to attach it to multiple possible sites simultaneously. In our study, participants tried to attach the disambiguating verb to the closest noun, irrespective of whether the resulting structure was globally coherent or grammatically sound. When the closest noun yielded a globally plausible interpretation, participants showed a reduced tendency to explore alternative attachments. Conversely, when the closest noun did not lead to a coherent interpretation, they tended to attach the disambiguating verb both to the closest noun and to a preceding noun in most cases.

One option for further exploring the potentially incoherent nature of the final representation could involve, for example, using multiple comprehension questions at the same time. While the task demands might push participants into adopting a coherent representation more strongly or make them more aware of the intended representation of the structure, it is also possible that those participants who were not able to construct a coherent representation or ended up confused might provide contradictory answers to a given set of questions. Obtaining such results with this experimental design would strongly support the option that comprehenders sometimes fail to reanalyze garden-path sentences fully and in accordance with the input, opting for constructing multiple locally plausible strings instead.

In the Introduction, we mentioned that multiple explanations exist for why the initial misanalysis of garden-path sentences lingers as well as various theories about the final representation of such sentences. One widely discussed explanation suggests that comprehenders

manage to reanalyze the sentences, building a globally coherent and grammatical syntactic representation, but fail to inhibit the initial misanalysis, which remains active in memory and interferes with the correct interpretation. An alternative view posits that comprehenders build multiple locally licit, partial representations that cannot be integrated into a globally coherent and grammatical whole. Our results are more consistent with the second view. For example, in the case of the MV/RR sentences, participants may create partial representations such as *the professor awarded the grant*, *the grant gained more attention*, and *the professor gained more attention*; for the NP/Z sentences, the local interpretations might be *the assistant shaved the actor* and *the actor watched the sports news*, occasionally accompanied by *the assistant watched the sports news*. Participants may then rely on these local strings to construct an overall interpretation of the sentence meaning, but a coherent global syntactic structure may never fully emerge.

This explanation aligns with the findings of Slattery et al. (2013) and subsequent replications (Huang & Ferreira, 2021; Qian et al., 2018). Slattery et al. observed a gender mismatch effect on the reflexive pronoun in sentences like (12), which they interpreted as evidence of successful reanalysis.

(12) After the bank manager telephoned David's mother grew worried and gave himself approximately 5 days to reply.

Similarly to our experiment, we can assume that participants created the following partial representations: *the bank manager telephoned David's mother* and *David's mother grew worried and gave himself approximately 5 days to reply*. The gender mismatch between *mother* and *himself* could still arise, even if the first part of the sentence was not reanalyzed. Subsequently, the elevated first-pass times on *himself off* in sentences like (13) may not result from interference between the initial misanalysis and the correct analysis but rather from participants encountering new (and possibly unexpected) information, since up until this point they only understood that *Frank was drying off the truck*.

(13) While Frank dried off the truck that was dark green was peed on by a stray dog. Frank quickly finished drying himself off then yelled out the window at the dog.

It is important to note that one limitation of our study is the fact that comprehension questions do not directly measure what is happening during online parsing. Since the responses reflect post-hoc processes and may be influenced by factors such as decay, interference, phrasing of the questions, and other task-related effects (Bader & Meng, 2018; Chromý & Tomaschek, 2024; Ferreira & Yang, 2019; Meng & Bader, 2021), it remains possible that a globally coherent syntactic structure is built during processing but becomes disrupted later. For instance, the low response accuracy to the question regarding the correct analysis of the ambiguous region may indeed be caused by interference between the correct interpretation and the initial misinterpretation, although it is unclear why this would exert such a significant effect, as we previously mentioned.

The responses might also reflect representations which participants created on the spot, as a result of reading the questions, and not the original representation of the sentence (which decays while the question is being read). For example, questions targeting potential misanalyses in our experiment, such as *Did the professor award the grant?* or *Did the professor gain more attention?*, may trigger the creation of corresponding analyses, even though the original representation of the sentence they created did not involve such strings. Consequently, this may lead to a higher proportion of incorrect “yes” responses to these questions.

On the other hand, if readers responded according to the interpretation they created while reading the questions, the accuracy should be quite high when the correct response to the question is “yes” (such as with *Did the assistant shave himself?* or *Did the professor gain the attention?*). While the DISCOR questions show this exact pattern, what we observe with the AMBCOR questions in our experiment is the opposite: Participants often respond with a “no” even though the phrasing of the question should lead to a correct “yes” response. This could mean two things: Either reading the

question triggers the creation of a representation that is contradictory to what the question says, or the response accuracy would be even lower if the question targeting this region was phrased differently. This indicates that the pattern we observed is not caused by the phrasing of the comprehension questions only. Moreover, the fact that there are significant differences between the conditions suggests that the way the participants in our experiment interpreted the stimuli is, at least to an extent, influenced by ambiguity.

Nevertheless, it is good to bear in mind that similarly to other psycholinguistic studies, this difference might only be present in combination with the specific experimental design we used and might not appear in a different experimental setting or outside of lab. For example, Ceháková and Chromý (2023) demonstrate a difference in response accuracy rates for garden-path sentences depending on the experimental task – accuracy was significantly higher with yes or no questions than with open-ended questions. The presence of comprehension questions might, for example, cause participants to adopt a more shallow processing strategy or force them to settle on a specific interpretation, while their general representations of the sentences were more vague. Being repeatedly exposed to garden-path structures might also play a role (Dempsey et al., 2024; Prasad & Linzen, 2021).

With that said, the results of our experiment still point out the limitations of the previous studies on garden-path sentences that followed a similar experimental design. Participants frequently do not appear to reanalyze the ambiguous region at all, and they seem to maintain more than one representation of the disambiguating region, especially in the case of the MV/RR sentences.

Nevertheless, the results still align well with the general ideas of the good-enough approach to language comprehension (Ferreira et al., 2002; Karimi & Ferreira, 2016) that the above-mentioned studies also supported. Within this approach, reanalysis of garden-path sentences is not an all-or-nothing phenomenon. Rather than leading to either a perfectly veridical representation of the input or failing entirely, reanalysis may also produce something in between—it might be “good enough.” The current consensus seems to be that a full and proper syntactic representation is built during reanalysis. What is “good enough” is the process of reanalysis itself, which fails to fully inhibit the initial misanalysis. According to this view, the parser lays the correct syntactic structure, built during reanalysis, on top of the initial misparse using a mechanism called Overlay (Lau & Ferreira, 2005). The erroneous structure then decays over time but can still interfere with the new structure. Our results, on the other hand, suggest that it is the structural representation that is good enough, at least in some cases. The final representation might not be globally coherent and grammatical, and it might contain multiple possible analyses of the problematic regions simultaneously.

The option that comprehenders do not build a proper, globally coherent structure but maintain multiple locally plausible analyses instead is also consistent with another assumption of the good-enough approach: that fully ambiguous structures may remain underspecified unless comprehenders are prompted toward disambiguation by task demands. There is ample evidence showing that people do not attempt to disambiguate such structures and simply maintain the ambiguity until the need for disambiguation arises (Gilbert et al., 2021; Swets et al., 2008; Tan & Foltz, 2020). A similar situation might easily arise with locally ambiguous structures: Comprehenders might not attempt to fully disambiguate the structure and instead maintain multiple possible solutions to conserve their cognitive resources.

The construction of multiple local parses can also be explained by self-organizing models of sentence processing (Smith et al., 2021; Tabor et al., 2004). These models assume that the human parsing mechanism does not operate under grammatical supervision; in other words, even strings that are not grammatically licit can be constructed during sentence processing. The final analysis is created through the mechanism of self-organization: The words in a sentence activate small pieces of syntactic structure called treelets. The treelets interact and connect with each other freely until they reach a state of harmony and settle on a final analysis, which is usually, but not always, grammatical.

This approach can also explain the coexistence of multiple interpretations of both the ambiguous and disambiguating regions observed in our experiment (e.g., *the professor gained more attention, the*

grant gained more attention, the professor awarded the grant, and the assistant shaved the actor, the actor watched the sports news, the assistant watched the sports news). These structures may all be created at some point during processing and receive enough support to be maintained until the end.

It might also be the case that comprehenders are confused or unsure about how to analyze the input, and the self-organizing mechanism is used in an effort to build at least some kind of representation when a globally coherent structure cannot be easily constructed (cf. Paape et al., 2023; Tabor et al., 2004). Our results are largely consistent with this option. Both garden-path structures we used are demanding to analyze and may easily lead to processing failure. In that case, comprehenders might resort to building and maintaining multiple locally plausible structures in order to interpret the sentence in some way, even though such structures are not grammatical and cannot be combined into a coherent whole.

Our results can also be explained by noisy channel processing (Levy, 2008b). This approach assumes that comprehenders are accustomed to being uncertain about the exact form of the input they receive (due to factors like noise, inattention, errors made by the speaker, etc.) and might update their beliefs about it according to their experience with what kind of input is common in order to build a full and unproblematic representation. In the case of our experiment, it is possible that the participants made slight changes to the NP/Z structure in example (11) if they deemed it ungrammatical or confusing. For instance, they might have believed that a pronoun was accidentally omitted from some part of the sentence and thus thought that the intended structure resembled one of the sentences in (14):

- (14) a. While the assistant shaved *him*, the actor who was overworked watched the sports news.
b. While the assistant shaved the actor who was overworked, *he* watched the sports news.

Similar examples can also be created for the MV/RR structure in (15):

- (15) a. The professor awarded the grant *which* gained more attention from marine biologists.
b. The professor awarded the grant *and* gained more attention from marine biologists.
c. The professor *who* awarded the grant gained more attention from marine biologists.

None of these representations can explain the coexistence of all the representations we documented in our experiment (e.g., both the *professor* and the *grant* gaining more attention) if we consider them individually. However, if we assume that the participants edited the structures in different ways and/or that different items were edited differently and that all of these changes were reflected in the results to some extent, we can arrive at the same outcomes shown in the experiment.

This leads us directly to the question of diversity in sentence processing. Recent studies indicate that participants tend to adopt different strategies when (re)reading sentences (Paape & Vasishth, 2022) and that they reach different processing outcomes (Ceháková & Chromý, 2023). There is also considerable variation in effect sizes for individual items in studies measuring reaction times in garden-path sentences (Huang et al., 2024). The results of our experiment fit well into this narrative, as they demonstrate significant differences in the processing of different types of syntactic structures. Specifically, the interpretation of the disambiguating region was handled quite differently in the NP/Z ambiguity compared to the MV/RR ambiguity, and these differences were linked to the structural properties of the sentences. This further emphasizes the importance of not limiting research on garden-path sentences to a single type of structure. Since different types of structures yield significantly different processing outcomes, the conclusions drawn from studying a specific type of structure (e.g., the commonly used NP/Z ambiguity) should not be generalized. Moreover, comparing different types of structures may provide important insights into the factors influencing how sentences are processed and interpreted.

We also stress the methodological importance of asking the right comprehension questions, not limiting research to probing the initial misanalysis of sentences, and focusing on other regions as well. Studies focusing on garden-path sentences typically use two comprehension questions: one that targets

the initial misanalysis of the ambiguous region and another that targets the correct analysis of that region. However, these two questions alone would fail to capture the fact that the ambiguous region was not interpreted correctly in either of the two types of sentences in our experiment and would not they reflect the differences in the interpretation of the disambiguating region that we detected. In fact, relying solely on these questions could create the impression that both sentence types are processed very similarly and are successfully reanalyzed. Only by adding the other two questions did we reveal that the actual situation is quite different. With this, we advocate for incorporating more diversity in future research on garden-path sentences, both in terms of materials (sentence structures and comprehension questions) and in the conclusions about the strategies comprehenders adopt.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used GPT-4 to enhance the readability and clarity of the text. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed, and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Appendix A

Figure A1. Response accuracy for individual items in all conditions.